

Stellar counts versus V and I magnitudes

L Lindegren, 1998 Jan 8 (SAG_LL_012)

INTRODUCTION

A standard galaxy model has been used to calculate $N(m,l,b)$ (the density of stars brighter than magnitude m for galactic coordinates l, b), where m is either the V or I magnitude. The program used is essentially GRMOD by Gilmore and co-workers (ca 1986–1997) with default values for most galactic parameters. That program produces detailed colour/magnitude data, for the different galactic components, and for any given direction. Thus much more information is available than just the total counts $N(m,l,b)$ considered here, e.g. the colour distribution at each point, and the fraction of stars in each galactic component.

Analytical functions were fitted to the counts, allowing $N(m,l,b)$ to be recovered (typically to within 10%) by a compact subroutine appended to this note. Additional subroutines give the longitude-averaged counts $N(m,b)$ and the sky-averaged counts $N(m)$, where m is either the V or I magnitude.

THE MODEL

The galaxy model contains three components: disk (old Pop I), thick disk (intermediate Pop II), and halo (extreme Pop II spheroid). The disk has a radial scale length of 3.5 kpc and a scale height of 325 pc for MS stars and 250 pc for RG and WD. The thick disk has a radial scale length of 3.5 kpc and a scale height of 1.3 kpc. The halo density follows an $r^{1/4}$ law with effective radius 2.7 kpc and minor/major axis ratio 0.8. The local number density ratio for the three components is 1:0.02:0.00125. Luminosity functions, colour-magnitude relations, photometric relations and reddening laws have been adopted from observations as appropriate for each component. The extinction follows the Sandage (modified cosec) law with a scale height of 100 pc. The model thus ignores all small-scale effects and is not expected to produce realistic results near the galactic plane. No attempt was made (in this first approximation) to calibrate the galactic parameters by means of actual star counts (cf. comparison in next section).

SAMPLE RESULTS

The tables below give a sample of results in the form $\lg N(<m)$, with N (in stars per square degree) averaged over longitude and over the whole sky. The first table, for visual magnitudes, gives a comparison with Allen (Astrophysical Quantities, 1973, p. 244) for the sky average. There is a systematic difference of 0.2 to 0.3 dex in the sense that Allen gives a higher number density. This difference persists at all magnitudes and galactic latitudes. For $V < 10$ the density given by Allen ($\lg N = 0.91$) is only slightly below the Tycho counts ($\lg N = 0.945$). From Figure 1 in SAG_ML_003 we have $\lg N(I < 21) = 3.65$ at high galactic latitudes (which $b?$), while the model gives 3.488 at $b=90$ (and 3.64 at $b=60$). At the galactic centre ($l=b=0$) the model predicts $\lg N(I < 20) = 5.725$.

The model parameters could probably be adjusted to give a fair representation of the actual **large-scale** distribution of stars on the sky. For this some additional empirical calibration will be required, which in the future may result in improved versions of the subroutines.

Table 1. $\lg N(<V)$ [stars per square degree] averaged over galactic longitude and over the whole sky, according to the model. The column AQ3 is the sky average from Allen (1973).

V	b=0	b=5	b=10	b=20	b=30	b=60	b=90	sky	AQ3
12.0	1.751	1.752	1.743	1.665	1.544	1.234	1.160	1.556	1.76
13.0	2.275	2.267	2.218	2.085	1.935	1.603	1.524	1.994	2.17
14.0	2.708	2.694	2.618	2.450	2.279	1.925	1.838	2.372	2.56
15.0	3.105	3.085	2.985	2.781	2.591	2.209	2.110	2.719	2.94
16.0	3.485	3.460	3.331	3.089	2.875	2.458	2.347	3.047	3.29
17.0	3.842	3.809	3.648	3.363	3.124	2.673	2.553	3.350	3.64
18.0	4.170	4.130	3.939	3.612	3.349	2.869	2.744	3.632	3.95
19.0	4.474	4.428	4.210	3.845	3.559	3.052	2.924	3.897	4.20
20.0	4.776	4.722	4.468	4.057	3.748	3.226	3.092	4.156	4.5
21.0	5.078	5.011	4.705	4.236	3.909	3.389	3.245	4.406	4.7
22.0	5.342	5.262	4.903	4.382	4.046	3.538	3.382	4.626	
23.0	5.536	5.448	5.059	4.510	4.168	3.665	3.500	4.797	
24.0	5.684	5.594	5.195	4.633	4.286	3.772	3.604	4.937	
25.0	5.813	5.722	5.319	4.749	4.393	3.863	3.695	5.061	

Table 2. $\lg N(<I)$ [stars per square degree] averaged over galactic longitude and over the whole sky, according to the model.

I	b=0	b=5	b=10	b=20	b=30	b=60	b=90	sky
12.0	2.466	2.434	2.279	2.011	1.799	1.450	1.374	2.001
13.0	2.922	2.877	2.671	2.355	2.138	1.816	1.728	2.396
14.0	3.316	3.262	3.023	2.678	2.461	2.149	2.045	2.753
15.0	3.650	3.594	3.344	2.991	2.772	2.445	2.326	3.075
16.0	3.951	3.897	3.653	3.301	3.069	2.702	2.575	3.376
17.0	4.243	4.191	3.955	3.594	3.341	2.926	2.799	3.663
18.0	4.548	4.494	4.247	3.861	3.584	3.133	3.005	3.947
19.0	4.868	4.807	4.530	4.103	3.804	3.327	3.191	4.230
20.0	5.191	5.120	4.802	4.326	4.005	3.503	3.353	4.510
21.0	5.479	5.398	5.039	4.515	4.173	3.649	3.488	4.761
22.0	5.710	5.623	5.234	4.673	4.313	3.770	3.604	4.967
23.0	5.909	5.816	5.400	4.806	4.430	3.874	3.706	5.145
24.0	6.092	5.991	5.546	4.916	4.528	3.970	3.797	5.308
25.0	6.258	6.150	5.669	5.002	4.606	4.055	3.875	5.453

SUBROUTINES

Below are listed three Fortran functions,
 REAL*4 FUNCTION cumloc(typ, amag, along, alat)
 REAL*4 FUNCTION cumave(typ, amag, alat)
 REAL*4 FUNCTION cumsky(typ, amag)

Arguments are:

CHARACTER*1 typ = 'V' or 'I' for the type of magnitude

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REAL*4 amag      = magnitude limit
REAL*4 alon, alat = galactic longitude and latitude in deg
                  (alon is not restricted to 0-360 deg)

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The returned function value is N, the density of stars brighter than the specified magnitude limit, in stars per square degree. cumloc() gives the local density at a specified sky position, cumave() gives the density averaged over longitude, and cumsky() gives the density averaged over the whole sky.

Due to the model assumptions the densities are symmetric about the galactic plane (alat = 0) and galactic meridian (alon = 0 or 180 deg). This may not necessarily be the case for future versions of the subroutines.

To check that the subroutines runs correctly on your computer, compile with the supplied main program and execute; the output should be: 15354.08 34736.36 (or very close to that).

```

PROGRAM main
  dv = cumsky('V', 20.123)
  di = cumsky('I', 20.123)
  WRITE(*, '(1x,2f10.2)') dv, di
END
C*****
  FUNCTION cumsky(typ, amag)
C*****
C
C  Calculates the cumulative density (stars/deg^2) of stars brighter
C  than typ = amag, where typ is 'I' or 'V', averaged over the sky.
C
C  Version 1 (LL 1997 Jan 8)
C
C  Calls FUNCTION cumave().
C
  CHARACTER typ*1
  PARAMETER (pi = 3.14159265, rad = pi/180.0)
  n = 90
  d = 1./float(n)
  sum = 0.
  DO sinlat = 0.5*d, 1., d
    alat = asin(sinlat)/rad
    sum = sum + cumave(typ, amag, alat)
  ENDDO
  cumsky = sum*d
  RETURN
END
C*****
  FUNCTION cumave(typ, amag, alat)
C*****
C
C  Calculates the cumulative density (stars/deg^2) of stars brighter
C  than typ = amag, where typ is 'I' or 'V', averaged over galactic
C  longitude, as function of galactic latitude (alat) in degrees.
C
C  Version 1 (LL 1997 Jan 8)
C
C  Calls FUNCTION cumloc().
C
  CHARACTER typ*1
  PARAMETER (pi = 3.14159265, rad = pi/180.0)
  n = nint(11.0*cos(rad*alat))
  dlon = 180./float(n+1)

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        sum = 0.5*(cumloc(typ,amag,0.,alat) +
        ,          cumloc(typ,amag,180.,alat))
    DO i = 1, n
        alon = float(i)*dlon
        sum = sum + cumloc(typ, amag, alon, alat)
    ENDDO
    cumave = sum/float(n+1)
    RETURN
    END
C*****
      FUNCTION cumloc(typ, amag, alon, alat)
C*****
C
C  Calculates the cumulative density (stars/deg^2) of stars brighter
C  than typ = amag, where typ is 'I' or 'V', as function of galactic
C  longitude (alon) and latitude (alat), both in degrees.
C
C  Version 1 (LL 1997 Jan 8)
C
C  Uses analytical fits to densities calculated by the GALAXY model
C  program GRMOD (Gilmore et al, 1986-97)
C
C  Valid only in the magnitude range 12.0 <= amag <= 25.0.
C  Outside this range it gives an exponential extrapolation which
C  may or may not be reasonable.
C
      PARAMETER (pi = 3.14159265, rad = pi/180.0)
      PARAMETER (mag = 14)
      CHARACTER*1 typ
      REAL t(0:6), q(0:6), ci(12,mag), cv(12,mag), cm(12), amags(mag)
      LOGICAL first
      SAVE first, ci, cv, amags, dmag
C
C  Definition of coefficients for each whole magnitude:
C  iqi(1,) = 10*amag
C  iqi(2:5,) = 1000*q(0,0:3)
C  iqi(6:8,) = 1000*q(1,1:3)
C  iqi(9:13,) = 1000*q(2,6,1)
C  where lg(dens(I<amag)) = sum_i sum_j q(i,j)*cos(i*L)*(1-sin|B|)**j
C
      INTEGER iqi(13,mag), iqv(13,mag)
      DATA iqi/
+120,1374,465,748,-18,285,-199,151,31,9,4,2,1,
+130,1728,644,-54,739,366,-460,415,51,19,11,7,4,
+140,2045,834,-670,1250,478,-840,763,66,28,16,11,6,
+150,2326,963,-872,1366,613,-1250,1089,73,32,19,13,7,
+160,2575,981,-595,1105,719,-1452,1198,75,33,19,13,8,
+170,2799,917,-109,738,766,-1388,1079,77,33,20,14,8,
+180,3005,890,116,642,822,-1339,980,80,33,19,13,8,
+190,3191,958,-27,858,946,-1487,1044,92,36,20,13,7,
+200,3353,1075,-321,1190,1114,-1778,1238,114,47,26,17,10,
+210,3488,1166,-551,1473,1312,-2241,1577,132,55,31,21,12,
+220,3604,1184,-608,1630,1499,-2646,1834,139,58,32,21,12,
+230,3706,1180,-693,1828,1666,-2912,1951,145,59,33,22,12,
+240,3797,1221,-1002,2207,1812,-3067,1972,154,62,34,22,12,
+250,3875,1309,-1508,2728,1945,-3212,2010,166,67,36,24,13/
      DATA iqv/
+120,1160,403,1261,-1092,224,-108,-38,7,1,0,0,0,
+130,1524,450,1127,-808,272,-138,-23,13,3,1,0,0,
+140,1838,516,1005,-613,336,-183,-3,24,7,3,2,1,
+150,2110,619,842,-416,432,-323,100,41,15,8,5,3,
+160,2347,716,741,-265,560,-602,328,60,26,15,11,6,
+170,2553,771,736,-165,732,-1063,700,73,32,19,14,8,

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+180,2744,782,778,-77,943,-1535,1019,81,34,20,14,8,
+190,2924,787,762,67,1108,-1694,1040,93,37,20,14,8,
+200,3092,847,479,434,1217,-1693,969,114,46,25,17,9,
+210,3245,977,-96,1032,1311,-1844,1104,136,57,32,21,12,
+220,3382,1125,-702,1615,1416,-2194,1437,150,63,35,24,13,
+230,3500,1214,-1011,1908,1518,-2553,1750,155,64,36,24,13,
+240,3604,1223,-987,1915,1614,-2816,1938,156,64,36,24,13,
+250,3695,1190,-848,1848,1717,-3011,2033,156,64,35,23,13/
C
DATA first/.TRUE./
C
C On first call convert iqi, iqv data to real data ci, cv, amags:
C
IF (first) THEN
DO m = 1, mag
amags(m) = 0.1*float(iqi(1,m))
DO i = 1, 12
ci(i,m) = 0.001*float(iqi(i+1,m))
cv(i,m) = 0.001*float(iqv(i+1,m))
ENDDO
ENDDO
dmag = (amags(mag) - amags(1))/float(mag-1)
first = .FALSE.
ENDIF
C
C Interpolate coefficients for relevant type to amag:
C
m = min0(mag-1,max0(1,nint((amag-amags(1))/dmag + 0.5)))
h = (amag - amags(m))/dmag
IF (typ .EQ. 'I') THEN
DO i = 1, 12
cm(i) = (1.-h)*ci(i,m) + h*ci(i,m+1)
ENDDO
ELSEIF (typ .EQ. 'V') THEN
DO i = 1, 12
cm(i) = (1.-h)*cv(i,m) + h*cv(i,m+1)
ENDDO
ELSE
WRITE(*,'(a,a)') 'wrong magnitude type in cumloc: ', typ
STOP
ENDIF
C
C Calculate Chebyshev polynomials t(i) = Ti(cos(alon)):
C
x = cos(rad*alon)
x2 = 2.*x
t(0) = 1.
t(1) = x
DO i = 2, 6
t(i) = x2*t(i-1) - t(i-2)
ENDDO
C
C Calculate Fourier coefficients for given latitude:
C
y = 1.0 - amax1(0.07,sin(abs(rad*alat)))
q(0) = cm(1) + y*(cm(2) + y*(cm(3) + y*cm(4)))
q(1) = y*(cm(5) + y*(cm(6) + y*cm(7)))
q(2) = y*cm(8)
q(3) = y*cm(9)
q(4) = y*cm(10)
q(5) = y*cm(11)
q(6) = y*cm(12)
C

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c  Finally sum the Fourier (cosine) series:
c
    sum = 0
    DO  i = 0, 6
        sum = sum + q(i)*t(i)
    ENDDO
    cumloc = 10.0**sum
    RETURN
    END
```